

Effect of Public Debt on Welfare of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs). A Case Study of Kafue District

Alex Chishimba¹ and Peter Silwimba^{2a}

¹School of Humanities and Business, Information and Communications University, Lusaka, Zambia

²Risk Department, National Savings and Credit Bank

^aSchool of Humanities and Business, Information and Communications University, Lusaka, Zambia

^aCorresponding Author: Peter Silwimba, Emailsilwimbap47@gmail.com

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ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Published on 23rd Dec 2025</p> <p>Keywords: Public debt Interest rate Investment Profit SMEs Credit terms</p>	<p>In recent years, public debt has become a significant concern for both policymakers and economists globally, particularly as it has been observed to influence the welfare of Small and Medium Enterprises (SME). Public debt can provide financial support to boost growth, infrastructure development, and performance of Small and Medium Enterprises. However, excessive borrowing or poor debt management can lead to inflationary pressures, high tax burdens, and reduced public investment. This study examined the influence of public debt on the welfare of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Kafue District, with a specific focus on three specific objectives. The first being, SMEs spending on production. The impact on investment capacity of SMEs and lastly, credit accessibility of SMEs in Kafue. A conceptual framework effectively illustrated the relationship between public debt (independent variable) and the welfare of Small and Medium Enterprises (dependent variable). A cross-sectional research design was employed, and quantitative data were collected from a sample of 50 SMEs selected through stratified random sampling. Primary data were gathered using a structured questionnaire and analyzed using SPSS, employing descriptive statistics, Chi-square tests, ANOVA, and regression analysis. Among others, the results revealed that SMEs in Kafue face increasing production costs, particularly in relation to utility expenses. Descriptive results revealed that electricity (36%) and water supply (32%) were the most essential utilities for business operations. A notable 32% of respondents reported that utility bills had shifted from affordable to barely affordable, largely attributed to high taxes (40%) and the inflation (30%). The regression model assessing determinants of SME profitability was statistically significant ($R^2 = 0.607$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that 60.7% of variations in profitability were explained by investment levels, utility spending, and credit access. All predictors were significant, with utility bills ($\beta_2 = 0.687$, $p < 0.001$), investment rate ($\beta_1 = 0.261$, $p = 0.009$), and credit allocation ($\beta_3 = 0.368$, $p < 0.001$) contributing positively to profitability. The study also reveals that SMEs are highly responsive to the economic factors such as; high taxes, high interest rates, and the nature of requirements for guarantors dissuade SMEs from accessing credit. Thus, the study concludes that public debt management is key to welfare and financial sustainability for SMEs.</p>

1. Introduction

1.1 Background

Small and medium sized firms play a prominent role in economic development (Osotimehi, et al. 2012). The importance of SMEs cannot be overemphasized in an economy. This is because they contribute to the creation of employment, free competitive market environments, inputs for large scale industries and so on. Drucker (1985) stated that entrepreneurship is not complete without the injection of innovation. In any business endeavor, the putting together of innovation and entrepreneurship by an SME will need a very important spice of creativity to ensure a quick growth and development process in its environment. It is pertinent to understand that 'creativity and Innovation' are the engine house of economic growth. Public debt plays a crucial role in shaping the economic and financial well-being of SMEs. It refers to the total amount of money that households owe to financial institutions, including loans, mortgages, credit card debt, and other forms of borrowing. While debt can serve as a tool for financial growth by enabling investments in funds, education, and business ventures, excessive public debt can lead to financial

distress, high borrowing costs, and reduction in credit accessibility. The ultimate goal of any enterprise activity is the maximization of profit, so it is unsurprising that well-being has always been one of the main issues of interest to economists. Well-being can be treated as a multifaceted research category that covers both the material and non-material spheres of business. The former includes the condition of owned real estate, durable goods or other tangible resources, and the financial situation, while the latter includes the labor market, the sense of security, social integration, and the forms of, and opportunities for, spending leisure time. Purchasing power determines the satisfaction of investment decisions and business well-being. Under developed financial market conditions, firms can make intertemporal substitutions of consumption. Access to credit and loans means that current consumption can be increased beyond the level of actual income earned. Yet the higher the level of debt, the more likely it is that the full force of its negative impact will reveal itself. In Zambia, public debt has an impact on access to credit facilities, microfinance institutions, and informal lending sources. The situation in Kafue District, a significant economic hub for trade, reflects national trends where many companies and enterprises depend on credit funds for business activities. The ability of business firms to manage their finances effectively has direct implications on their overall welfare of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs). This study aims to analyze the impact of public debt on the welfare of Small and Medium Enterprises, focusing on Kafue District.

1.2 Statement of the problem

Despite the financial support public debt may provide, especially to SMEs, they continue to face challenges in accessing affordable finances to aid their production and investment capacities. This is because excessive borrowing or poor debt management can lead to high tax burdens, and reduced public investment. This demand for an examination of how public debt influences spending on production, investment capacity, credit access, and overall welfare of SMEs within Kafue District. The accumulation in public debt has raised concerns about financial sustainability and economic resilience. Many businesses face challenges in balancing the inflationary costs with expected returns, leading to lower investment opportunities that hinder long-term financial progress. It is against this background that this study seeks to examine how public debt influences investment capacity, credit access, and overall welfare of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Kafue district.

1.3. Research Objective

The general and specific objectives of this study are as presented in the sections below

1.3.1 General Objective

To analyze the impact of public debt on the welfare of Small and Medium Enterprises in Kafue District.

1.3.2 Specific Objectives

- i. To ascertain how public debt accumulation influences spending of SMEs on production in Kafue district.
- ii. To assess the effects of public debt on investment capacity of SMEs in Kafue district.
- iii. To evaluate how public debt accumulation effects credit accessibility of SMEs in Kafue District

1.4 Research Questions

- i. How does public debt influence the spend of Small and Medium Enterprises on production in Kafue district?
- ii. What is the relationship between public debt levels welfare of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Kafue district?
- iii. What coping mechanisms does government use to manage internal and external shocks of public debt?

1.5 Conceptual Framework

This shows the diagrammatic depiction of the relationship between public debt and welfare of SMEs with variables (investment capacity, purchasing power and credit accessibility) determinants.

Figure 1.1 conceptual mechanisms by which public debt influences welfare of SMEs

The relationship between public debt and the welfare SMEs can be presented in Fig. 1. In the context of Kafue District, the burden of public debt may influence the economic environment, infrastructure development, fiscal policy effectiveness, and community resilience. In this conceptual framework, public debt is the independent variable, while the Welfare of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) represents the dependent variable. The model assumes a causal relationship, where changes in the magnitude or management of public debt directly or indirectly affect the welfare of local communities and businesses. Scholars commonly agree that the welfare of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) can be viewed from multiple aspects and that the effects of public debt are also multidimensional. Public debt may affect businesses in the aspects of welfare such as investment capacity, purchasing power and credit accessibility

1.6 Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on the Credit Rationing Theory developed by Stiglitz and Weiss (1981). The theory states that financial institutions do not allocate credit solely based on interest rates, but based on perceived risk and information asymmetry. Banks often limit lending to borrowers they view as risky, regardless of their willingness to pay higher interest rates.

In the context of rising public debt, government securities become more attractive to lenders because they offer higher returns and lower risk compared to SME lending. As a result, banks practice credit rationing, limiting the amount of credit available to SMEs, increasing collateral requirements, and imposing stricter loan conditions. This leads to reduced access to affordable financing for SMEs, constraining their ability to invest, expand operations, or improve profitability and welfare.

1.7 Significance of the Study

The primary importance of this study lies in its contribution to evidence-based policymaking. By examining the relationship between public debt and outcomes in SMEs in Kafue District, the research provides empirical insights into how national debt trends affect local livelihoods, investment climates, and access to social services. This localized analysis is particularly valuable for policymakers seeking to design debt management frameworks that are not only fiscally sound but also socially equitable.

2. Literature Review

2.1 The influence of public debt on the spending of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) on production in Kafue District.

At the global level, high public debt often increases country risk, leading to rising interest rates and reduced private investment flows (Panizza, 2009). Similarly, other global studies show that excessive public debt crowds out private sector borrowing and discourages productive investment (Rogoff, 2010). These global pressures ultimately shape how SMEs behave in production spending, cost planning, borrowing decisions, and long-term investment. When the funding is issued through equity, it can involve agency costs, “which are as result of conflict of interest between the various stakeholders of the company” (Jensen & Meckling, 1976).

SMEs are globally considered economic engines, as many large companies originated from them (Avevor, 2016). The crucial role of the SMEs in driving the economic growth of developing nations has been widely recognized (Mbuta, 2007). Excessive public debt disturbs global financial markets by increasing risk, tightening credit access and weakening the resilience of Small and Medium Enterprises (SME). The rising interest rates at a global scale reduce demand for business productions and restrict businesses from expanding expansion, while low rates stimulate investment and production. Onyiriuba (2016) posits that addressing the uncertainties and risks faced by banks in lending to SMEs is essential to stimulate growth.

Public debt has brought more challenges than benefits to SMEs that are in Africa. Many African nations, including Zambia, have struggled with export revenues that are not consistent, dependence on external borrowing, and global commodity markets with high volatility (Bank of Zambia, 2023; IMF, 2022; World Bank, 2023). Most reliable studies show that SMEs in Africa face challenges such as limited access to credit, high costs in their utility bills, and negative effects of inflation on business spending (Babalola et al., 2022; Ackah & Vuvor, 2011). The lack of Spending efficiently and poor planning— which are commonly documented in African SME — seem to increase the vulnerability to macroeconomic shocks caused by high public debt (Altman, 2013).

Furthermore, the policy about decentralization in Zambia has not fully empowered some districts like Kafue district. The delays in the government financial decisions at a central level which are pressured by the debt obligations limit the ability of government entities in the district to support SMEs and promote productive capacity (World Bank, 2023; Bank of Zambia, 2023). Then the result is that public debt continues to limit local economic growth and reduces the ability of SMEs to spend effectively on production. For instance, Authors such as Zimmermann and Muller (2009) claim that SMEs usually face risks in their operations that make it challenging to acquire debt finance in order to spend on production.

Lastly, the definition by Abor (2007) and Muhammad et al. (2022) explains debt financing as the ratio of the total debt to the total assets. Equity financing on the other hand is the ratio of the shareholder funds to the total liabilities (Hasan et al., 2017). With the creation of the Ministry of small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs), by the government, entrepreneurs have been urged to place themselves strategically. This is a good opportunity for SMEs aspiring to develop their businesses. However, funding business activities like production of good and services through issuance of equity give rise to agency costs “which are as result of conflict of interest between the various stakeholders of the company” (Jensen & Meckling, 1976).

2.2. The effects of public debt on Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) investment capacity

When investment capacity is examined on a global scale, public debt becomes a major factor in the welfare of investment. Public debt has a significant part to play in the global financial conditions that affect SME investment capacity. High debt increases the risk of investment in a country with debt, this also leads to raising interest rates and tightening credit markets, which reduces

SMEs' ability to access the needed financing (Reinhart and Rogoff, 2010; Panizza, 2009). This is very common in developing countries where SMEs depend primarily on financing from the banks due to weak capital markets (World Bank, 2023).

Some authors such as Jensen and Meckling (1976) believe that financing and investment decisions are connected processes that can impact the capital of a firm. Investment projects are usually challenging to keep track of and debtors are more likely to suffer from inadequate or insufficient investment, that according to Le and Obrien (2010). Due to such development the shareholders may engage in investments with high risk, which can create other problems (Jensen and Meckling, 1976).

Other studies from Reid (2003), Wiczorek-Kosmala et al., (2020) show that financing using equity plays a crucial role in the growth of Small and Medium Enterprises. For instance, Muller and Zimmermann (2009) argue that SMEs often face operational risks that make it challenging for them to obtain debt financing. The high risk associated with research and development projects makes equity financing to be even more essential for SMEs' investments in research and growth.

In addition to what was discussed earlier concerning debt financing and SME performance, there is limited information about SMEs despite the wide body of knowledge surround the topic studied (O'Brien, 2003; Muhammad et al., 2022). With new studies and new events, researchers have shifted their focus from large firms to SMEs. Studies on SMEs have indicated that there is a negative relationship between debt financing and performance. For example, Abor (2007) examined Ghanaian and South African SMEs and revealed that debt financing is negatively related to performance due to agency issues.

The effects of crowding out are quite predominant in African banking systems where governments borrow huge substantial amounts from domestic banks, putting a limit loan availability for SMEs in the process. (Ackah, 2011; Amonoo, 2003;). This situation is what now pushes SMEs to rely on informal credit or personal savings, which are not sufficient enough for long-term investment (Ackah, 2011). Poor financial literacy and limited business planning are the factors that reduce the SMEs' chances of securing loans in high debt environments (Aliyu, 2013).

Accumulation of debt at national level often triggers policy shifts such as increased taxations and subsidy reductions, which eventually influence SME credit accessibility. Majid (2015) points that macro-level adjustments weaken SME resilience and lower creditworthiness in the eyes of lenders. Further research adds that long-term lender to borrower relationships and supportive institutions can reduce credit rationing and stabilize SME performance in the challenging economic conditions (Atta et al., 2015; Stiglitz & Weiss, 1981). Therefore, when public debt forces a restrictive policy response, the institutions support structures that could lift the SME credit limitations become compromised.

In Zambia, the constant increases in public debt have limited government investment, and affected SMEs' ability to grow and reinvest in the economy. The high debt levels have contributed to the inflation, the high interest rates, all of which increase the cost of credit and reduce SMEs' access to financing (Bank of Zambia, 2023). Reports from world banks (2023) suggest that these macroeconomic pressures raise costs for imported material inputs and utilities. This reduces the small firms' capacity to invest in productive assets (Panizza, 2009). Another factor that discourages financial institutions from extending long-term credit is the decline in the investment capacity which is linked to uncertainty in Zambia's fiscal stance.

In the inner parts of Kafue district, SMEs are affected by unfinished infrastructure projects resulting from the high public debt, including unfinished road construction and poor supply of energy. As a result, this situation increases the cost of operation and reduces productivity (IMF, 2022; World Bank, 2023). SMEs in the local area also struggle with high collateral requirements, high lending rates, and limited access to government support programs due to the limitations in the budget which also strained with debt financing (Babalola, 2022).

2.3 The effects of public debt accumulation on Credit Accessibility Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs)

SME lending amounts to only 2% of total bank loans, i.e., the lowest in the world (Rocha, 2011). The credit environment in developing economies is affected by the accumulation of public debt. High level of debt particularly affect the ease with which SMEs access financial resources. This calls for a strong and stable private sector to step in under these conditions. Mbuta (2007) and Nuwagaba (2015) urge that economic growth largely depends on the efficiency of private enterprises. However, the weight of public debt is indirectly imposed on SME when attempting credit access, which eventually weakens the sector's ability to contribute effectively to the development of the nation.

The Trade-Off Theory of capital structure provides additional global insights into how firms balance debt and equity in financing production. It proposes that firms determine their optimal financing by balancing the tax advantages of debt against the cost of financial distress, such as the potential for bankruptcy (Litzenberger, 1973). A number of business firms use debt as way to benefit from tax shields, but they must compare this against possible financial distress and costs as confirmed by Baxter (1967). In addition to this, other scholars claim that tax policy and credit environments have a notable role in shaping SME capital structures globally (Fama & French, 2002).

On the other hand, Myers (1984) provided an alternative explanation, called the Pecking Order Theory, in which entrepreneurs prefer to use internal finance first because it is cheaper, followed by costlier external finance (i.e., debt and then equity) in cases where internal finance is insufficient. The continued burden of high public debt therefore remains a central constraint on SME financial resilience and expansion. Some empirical studies adopted this framework and find evidence supporting it (Mac an Bhaird, 2013; Sánchez-Vidal & Martín-Ugedo, 2005).

The most popular barrier that prevents SMEs from accessing formal credit is collateral, a requirement that if not met credit may not be issued. Writers like KPMG (2000) notes that a lot of SMEs in the sub Saharan region lack fixed assets, have a limited capital base, and informal business structures. Nyangoma (2012) also reports that collateral demands in Uganda can go as high as 150% in loan value, making borrowing impossible for the small firms. Similarly, Aryeetey et al., (1994) write that asymmetric information problems further amplify the constraints, as a number of SMEs lack reliable financial records, forcing banks to rely

heavily on collateral as a control measure. As a result, a lot of SMEs are excluded from the financial system despite their role in job creation and economic growth.

Zambia provides a clear illustration of how public debt accumulation affects SME access to credit through macroeconomic instability. Similarly, Roger et al. (2017) contend that the depreciation of the Kwacha in 2015 by nearly 40% triggered a spike in the inflation that increased operational costs for businesses and raised the real interest rates. Also Chipili (2022) asserts that the continuation of inflationary pressure between 2019 and 2024 was driven by rapid exchange rate, food shortages, and electricity tariff adjustments. Accumulation in public debt has been closely linked to these pressures, such as increased government borrowing which crowds out private investment and raises interest rates as indicated by Zambia's Ministry of Finance (2023).

Most of the Small Medium Enterprises that are operating with small profit margins are likely affected by the effects of debt on the nation because rising costs reduce their ability to fulfill repayment duties, weakening their credit appeal in the process. As many SMEs are aware, microfinance involves the supply of small loans to support a simple income-generating activity, a sentiment shared by Bateman, (2010). However, this type of loan is seldom exercised by banks, much more by specialized microfinance banks (Beck, 2013). As a result, the lending environment is tightened, such that even if SMEs show revenue potential, no consideration is attained. Ayyagari et al (2017) believe that this is due to the economic outcomes related to activities of firms in the formal sector.

2.4 Personal critique of literature review

While the literature review presents a wide-ranging discussion on public debt and its implications, by authors like Cowan (2015), Gozzi & Schmukler (2016). My critique centers on three limitations; limited integration of micro-level realities, lack of methods showing cross country findings and insufficient contextual depth. Scholars such as Cheleshe (2021), or Mwale & Zgambo (2020) could have been engaged to capture the structural and historical development of the debt crisis, weak industrialization, and relations to the global financial markets. Furthermore, the literature without a doubt, provides a rich starting point, however, my critique is that it requires deeper context, stronger engagement and a clearer connection to realities that SMEs are faced with, concerning public debt levels. Without these refinements, the literature risks being incomplete, particularly for a study seeking to understand how public debt affects the welfare of Zambian SMEs.

2.5 Establishment of Research Gaps

There are several gaps in research drawn from the analysis of public debt and its effects on the welfare of SMEs. First, global studies conducted by Reinhart and Rogoff (2010) focus on broad macroeconomic relationships between public debt and private investment but do not show how these effects manifest among SMEs in specific districts like Kafue. So this calls for future studies to investigate how rising debt levels affect SME outcomes at a local level. Finally, the attention to the social and environmental trade-offs associated with debt-financed projects in the small scale businesses industry is not sufficient enough. Instead, a closer examination of the opportunity costs of debt could provide a more holistic understanding of debt impacts on the SMEs.

3. Research Methodology

3.1 Research Methods

The research design used in this study was a cross-sectional study design, employing a quantitative methodology for gathering primary data (Wang, 2020).

3.2 Target Population

The target population for this study was SMEs in Kafue district who were estimated to be over 300 and most of these were officially registered.

3.3 Sample size

A sample size of 50 from the estimated population size done above sample size from our given estimated population.

3.4 Sampling

The sampling methodology for this study utilized a random sampling which was based on SME type (service, retail, manufacturing, informal) for research convenience.

3.5 Data Collection Methods

The primary research tool for this study was a simple structured questionnaire comprising closed-ended questions.

3.6 Data Analysis

Data analysis, Presentation of descriptive statistics was done using SPSS – Special Package for Social Science. For inferential statistics, ANOVA, and regression analysis is to be employed to establish associations between variables.

4. Findings and Results

4.1 Presentation of results on demographic characteristics of the respondents

The gender of respondents in this study is summarized as the study sample shows that 66% of the respondents was represented by males while females had a 34% threshold. A sign that the distribution of gender was inclusive. The age group distribution of respondents in Kafue district ranged from a minimum of 18 – 15 years to a maximum of 65 and Above years. The respondents from age group of 26 – 35, as the majority were middle-aged with some variation. The educational background of the respondents

in Kafue district is outlined as with the majority having Primary Education (46%) and secondary education (28%). A smaller portion had completed primary education. (20%), and only 6% had no formal education.

The types of businesses in Kafue district are shown as the majority (48%) represented retail businesses seconded by (32%) agriculture businesses, the Services (16%) and manufacturing business (4%) were the least represented. The registration of business of the respondents is that most of the respondents had their businesses or enterprises registered for operation, out all the total responses (78%) were registered, while a small percentage (22%) were not registered. The respondent's years in operation in Kafue district is reported with variations, in the number of years they have been in business, starting with the longest time being more than 6 years with a (44%) response, followed by 1- 3 year with 34% in response, 4-6 years with 16% and less than 1 year with a 6% threshold.

4.2. The influence of public debt on the spending of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) on production in Kafue District.

In this part of the thematic area, the major utility component is present in the figure 4.1 below

The Figure 4.1 Major utility component for business to achieve production

The analysis on this descriptive matter recorded that 36% of respondents selected Electricity supply, 32% of respondents selected water supply, 16% selected Gas supply and the last 16% selected Telecommunication/ internet.

In this part of the study analysis, the affordability of the utility bills then vs now of the respondents in Kafue district is presented in the figure below

Figure 4.2 Affordability of Utility Bills Then Vs Now

Nearly half of the respondents (32%) had reported the utility bills to have shifted from affordable to quite affordable credit or loans, while the majority (68%) are still able to afford their utility bills. while the majority (68%) are still able to afford their utility bills, nearly half of the respondents (32%) can barely afford their utility bills now compared to then. The cause of shift in the utility costs of respondents is highlighted in the figure below.

Figure 4.3 highlights the Major Cause of Shift in Utility Costs

A variety of reports emerged concerning the major cause of shift in utility bills. The outcome was that 40% of the reports pointed to High taxes, 30% pointed to Inflation, 24% pointed to climate change and 6% specified, showing high taxes to be a major cause. The regression of percentage profit of respondents of Kafue district is highlighted in the table below.

Table 4.1 regression analysis of percentage profit.

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.779 ^a	.607	.582	4.50351

a. Predictors: (Constant), credit allocation, 11. average utility bills 17. And percentage rate of investment

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	6.613	5.958		1.110	.273	-5.380	18.606
	11. Average, utility bills	.017	.002	.687	7.352	.000	.012	.022
	17. Percentage rate of investment	1.729	.632	.261	2.734	.009	.456	3.001
	Credit Allocation	.000	.000	.368	3.859	.000	.000	.000

a. Dependent Variable: percentage profitability

The overall model indicates that the regression model provides a strong explanation of SME percentage profit, with an R-squared of 0.607, meaning that 60.7% of the variation in SME profit is explained by utility spending, rate of investment, and credit accessed. The F-statistic of 23.72 with a p-value < 0.001 shows that the overall model is statistically significant, meaning the combination of predictors reliably explains SME profit.

The results of the regression show that all three predictors have positive and statistically significant coefficients, indicating that increases in utility spending, investment levels, and access to credit lead to higher SME profitability. Utility spending has a

modest effect, suggesting that reliable utilities enhance productivity, while investment shows a larger impact, meaning SMEs that invest more and achieve higher returns. Credit allocation contributes the least positively with a 0.000 coefficient value. The percentage distribution of profit in production with current utility costs of respondents in Kafue is outlined in the following table

Table 4.2 Percentage of Profits in Production with Current Utility Costs

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	10	1	2.0	2.0	2.0
	20	2	4.0	4.0	6.0
	30	8	16.0	16.0	22.0
	40	2	4.0	4.0	26.0
	50	13	26.0	26.0	52.0
	60	10	20.0	20.0	72.0
	70	3	6.0	6.0	78.0
	75	2	4.0	4.0	82.0
	80	9	18.0	18.0	100.0
	Total	50	100.0	100.0	

As shown in the table, percentage of profit was distributed as, respondents reported that 54% of profits in production. The reported percentages ranged from 10% to 80%, with a standard deviation of 18.93, suggesting a broad range of dependency on maize as a source of income.

4.3. The Effects Of Public Debt On Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) Investment Capacity

This thematic area of the second objective is characterized by the impact of high inflation on investment opportunities of the respondents is shown in the figure below.

Figure 4.4. Impact of high inflation on investment opportunities

The cost of high inflation was experienced in a number of outcomes which were reported by the respondents as follows; majority of 48% reported, increases cost of borrowing, 18% claimed it reduces purchasing power, another 18% claimed it reduces investment confidence and the last 16% claimed it increases risk of low returns on asset.

The relationship between the average revenue of business and percentage rate of investment in small businesses is summarized as indicated below.

Table 4.3. Average revenue of business and percentage rate of investment in small businesses

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1636.371	1	1636.371	401.503	.000 ^b
	Residual	195.629	48	4.076		
	Total	1832.000	49			
a. Dependent Variable: Average revenue of business						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Percentage rate of investment in small businesses						

The regression sum of squares is 1,636.371 with 1 degree of freedom (df), and the residual sum of squares is 195.629 with 48 degrees of freedom, leading to a total sum of squares of 1,832.000. The mean square for the regression is 1,636.371, and the residual mean square is 4.076.

The F-value is 401.503 with a p-value (Sig.) of 0.000, which within the significance threshold of 0.05. This indicates that the relationship between average revenue of business and percentage rate of investment in small businesses is statistically significant at the 5% level, suggesting a causal relationship where changes in rate of investment in small businesses may influence changes in average revenue.

4.4. The effects of public debt accumulation on Credit Accessibility Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs)

Under this thematic area of the third objective, promoting frequent access to loans/credit to grow the business among respondents in Kafue district is highlighted in the figure below.

Figure 4.5 Promoting Frequent Access to Loans/Credit To Grow the Business

According to the figure above, 80% of the respondents agreed to promoting frequent access to loans/credit to grow businesses, 12% of the respondents strongly agreed to promoting frequent access to loans/credit to grow businesses and 8% of the respondents were unsure of promoting frequent access to loans/credit to grow businesses.

The Association between Access to Credit/Loan and success of Credit Loan request of the respondents of Kafue is presented in the table below.

Table 4.4. Association between Access to Credit/Loan and success of Credit Loan request

Chi-Square Tests					
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	14.103 ^a	1	.000		
Continuity Correction ^b	11.655	1	.001		
Likelihood Ratio	18.394	1	.000		
Fisher's Exact Test				.000	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	13.821	1	.000		
N of Valid Cases	50				
a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 5.50.					
b. Computed only for a 2x2 table					

The Pearson Chi-Square value is 14.103 with 1 degrees of freedom (df) and a p-value of 0.000, which is less than the standard threshold of 0.05. This indicates a statistically significant association between Access to Credit/Loan and success of Credit Loan request

The Linear-by-Linear Association has a value of 13.821 with a p-value of 0.000, suggesting a significant linear trend in the relationship between Access to Credit/Loan and success of Credit Loan request.

The effect of taxation system on investment decisions among respondents Kafue district is presented in the figure below.

Figure 4.6 Effect of Taxation System on Investment Decisions

As indicated in the figure above, the majority of 44% had a negative effect from taxation system regarding investment decisions, 42% of the respondents had a neutral experience of taxation system regarding investment decisions and 14% of the respondents had a positive experience of taxation system regarding investment decisions.

The Influence of borrowing cost on ability to compete with other SMEs among the respondents is summarized as indicated in the figure below

Figure 4.7 Influence of borrowing cost on ability to compete with other SMEs

The figure indicates that 44% of respondents reported that the influence of borrowing cost on competing with other SMEs was negative, another 44% of respondents reported that the influence of borrowing cost on competing with other SMEs was Neutral and 12% of the respondent's report that the influence of borrowing cost on competing with other SMEs was positive.

The distribution of responses regarding aspect of credit access most affected due to government debt levels is presented in the figure below.

Figure 4.8 Aspect of Credit Access Most affected due to Government Debt levels

The distribution reports that majority of 52% respondents selected currency value to be the aspect most affected by government debt levels, 18% of the respondents selected Credit conditions as the aspect most affected by government debt levels, 16% of the respondents selected borrowing cost as the aspect most affected by government debt levels 14% of the respondents chose crowding as the aspect most affected by government debt levels.

The presentation of findings on the Most Popular Method government uses for debt management is given below.

Figure 4.9 Most Popular Method government use for debt management.

As indicated in the figure above the most effective method government uses for debt management was presented as 40% believe it is external debt restructuring, while 20% went for domestic fiscal reforms, 20% reported economic diversification and the remaining 20% of respondents reported fiscal consolidation.

5. Summary, Conclusion and Recommendations

5.1 Summary

In trying to ascertain the influence of Public debt on the spending of the SMEs, on production a regression analysis was implored and the results showed that all three predictors (i.e. utility spending, investment rate and credit access) have positive and statistically significant coefficients, indicating that increases in utility spending, investment levels, and access to credit lead to higher SME profitability. Utility spending has a modest effect of 0.017 unit, suggesting that reliable utilities enhance productivity, while investment shows a larger impact of 1.729, meaning SMEs that invest more and achieve higher returns. Credit allocation contributes the least positively with a 0.000 coefficient value.

Overall, the model summary shows that the independent variables jointly explain a considerable proportion of the variation in SME profitability. This suggests that financial management factors play a crucial role in determining SME success in Kafue District. However, the presence of both positive and negative relationships indicates that SMEs must balance their utility cost structure with productive investments and appropriate loan management to optimize profitability.

In addition, the ANOVA also highlighted a key factor about revenue and investment. After performing the ANOVA, it was discovered that the F-value is 401.503 with a p-value (Sig.) of 0.000, which within the significance threshold of 0.05. This indicates that the relationship between average revenue of business and percentage rate of investment in small businesses is statistically significant at the 5% level, suggesting a causal relationship where changes in rate of investment in small businesses may influence changes in average revenue.

The final aspect of this discussion was finding out the intent of the SMEs in Kafue district regarding the exploration of flexible investment ventures in the next 5 years to come. This was achieved using a descriptive analysis of frequencies distribution. Based on our findings, a majority 64% of respondents expressed intent to explore flexible investments in the next five years. This suggested optimism about the future of SME welfare among most participants.

5.2 Conclusion

There is no doubt that small and medium enterprises (SMEs) are not immune to the impact of public debt on an economy particularly the welfare of SMEs. We are fully of the major role SMEs play in economic development. That is enough reason for them to immediately become the economic priority of government because of their potentials if they have to address our economic flaws. Our track record in Zambia in the management of public debt accumulation has proved unsatisfactory. Even now, many of economic indicator of sustainable development cannot pass the test of efficient and effective management. Many SMEs collapsed while many are still grappling with inflation, credit unworthiness, and under-investment capacity. That proves that the credit rationing theory (CRT) is still influencing the actions of financial institutions on SMEs where access to credit is concerned. To

recall, the objective of this study was to analyze the impact of public debt on the welfare of Small and Medium Enterprises in Kafue District. Thus, the study concludes that excess public debt indirectly plays a major role in the welfare of SMEs. As such, SMEs should be sensitized about the factors that indicate the pressure of debt accumulation on their economy. Lastly, the study also concludes that good public debt management contribute to increased production and growth in profits for business.

5.3 Recommendations

The conclusion of this research study paved way for the following recommendations:

1. Improve Access to Affordable Credit for SMEs in Kafue and Countrywide

The excess public debt has led commercial banks to resort to credit rationing, stopping SMEs from accessing affordable financing. To address this, the government should implement credit-guarantee schemes, interest-rate caps for SME loans to reduce the cost of capital and support business growth.

2. Strengthen SME Literacy and Debt-Management Practices

knowledge in financial planning and loan negotiation leaves a lot to be desired on the part of SMEs to stay productive and profitable. Government agencies, banks, and SME support organizations should enhance training in financial literacy and investment planning to improve SME resilience.

3. Establish SME-Focused Public Debt Control Measures

Having the evidence that high public debt reduces private-sector lending, the Ministry of Finance should introduce policies that reserve a percentage of bank lending specifically for SMEs.

4. Promote Cooperatives and SME Credit Groups

In the same way farmers form cooperative for input benefits, promoting SME cooperatives can offer shared financing, bulk purchasing, and collective negotiation power. Cooperative structures reduce operational costs, improve creditworthiness, and allow SMEs to pool resources for expansion and investment.

5. Extend the Research and Coverage on SME financing

Lastly, the present study was confined to SMEs in Kafue. For further research coverage, it would be useful to carry out a similar study across all the provinces in Zambia and beyond and see whether new or same results would be uncovered.

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